

Deliverable D1.1

Data and Research Data Management Plan

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Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the approach for managing data generated and used by the AEGIS-OA project.

The plan outlines the types, sources, formats, and anticipated volumes of data, and establishes clear procedures for their processing and preservation in line with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.

It also defines the data governance framework as well as the allocation of roles and responsibilities among project partners and the resources required to support effective data management. Provisions for data security are included, covering secure storage, controlled access, and appropriate data sharing practices.

The DMP will be regularly updated to incorporate emerging project needs, data types, and ethical considerations.

1. Method

The project's Data Management Plan (DMP) has been developed in accordance with the guidelines provided by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template (v1.0, May 2021), as referenced in the Horizon Europe Programme Guide (v2.0, April 2022). These guidelines ensure alignment with FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and promote consistency in data handling practices across the consortium.

To support collaboration and continuous updates, the DMP will be maintained as a living document in the project's shared online environment. Project partners will contribute to plan updates through a collaborative spreadsheet, allowing real-time modifications as the project progresses, and new datasets are generated or reused. Updates to the DMP will be discussed as a standing agenda item during the Work Package Leaders meetings, while periodic snapshots will be archived for reporting purposes.

The structure of the live DMP is organized into a series of thematic sections/tabs, each addressing a key aspect of data management:

- **Reuse of previous data:** This section documents all external datasets and resources reused by the project. This ensures transparency regarding dependencies on pre-existing data and facilitates proper attribution and compliance with legal requirements.
- **Data generated by the project:** This section serves as an inventory of all datasets produced within the project. Each dataset is assigned a unique internal identifier (e.g., "DS1.2"), linked to the corresponding Work Package. The description includes data type, format, size, purpose, and potential reuse.
- **Findability:** This section outlines how datasets will be made discoverable. It specifies the use of persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs), metadata standards, indexing strategies, and the inclusion of machine-readable metadata to enhance visibility in repositories and search systems.
- **Accessibility:** This section defines how and under what conditions data can be accessed. It covers repository choices, access protocols (e.g., open or restricted access), authentication procedures where necessary, and any legal or ethical constraints affecting data availability.
- **Interoperability:** This section addresses the use of standardised formats, vocabularies, and ontologies to ensure that datasets can be integrated with other data and systems. It also considers mappings to widely used standards where project-specific formats are applied.
- **Reuse:** This section focuses on enabling future use of the data. It includes documentation practices, licensing conditions, provenance tracking, and quality

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assurance procedures to ensure that datasets remain understandable and updated beyond the project's lifetime.

- **Costs, Security and Ethics:** This section covers the resources required to implement FAIR data practices, as well as measures for data protection, long-term preservation, and compliance with ethical and legal frameworks (including GDPR where applicable).

All datasets described in the DMP are interlinked across these sections through their internal identifiers, ensuring consistency and traceability throughout the document. This structured and iterative approach allows the DMP to evolve during the project's timeline, and to maintain compliance with established standards.

2. Content

2.1 Reuse of previous data

Name	PID	Licence	For	Remarks
DDH User database	N/A	N/A	DDH trusted sources, administrators, editors	
DDH Journal database	N/A	N/A	DDH list of Diamond journals	
Knowledge base of scholarly indexes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19497543	CC-BY (xlsx, md)	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers, general public, media	
EDCH Forum User database	N/A	N/A	Administrators	
EDCH Registry Organisation database	N/A	N/A	Registry Administrators, DDH Administrators	
EDCH Registry User database	N/A	N/A	Registry Administrators, DDH Administrators	
EDCH training materials	N/A	CC-BY		<u>Available at</u> https://training.edch.eu/

2.2 Data generated by the project

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	WP1	Project	Text	Gdocs	<1GB	n/a	none	
DS1.2	Project deliverables	WP1	Project	Text	PDF	<1GB	All	As described in D1.3 Dissemination & Exploitation Plan	
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	WP1	Project	Text	PDF	<1GB	n/a	EC auditors	
DS1.4	Project website and the information contained therein	WP1	Project	Text, images, videos	html, png, pdf, mp4	<1TB	All	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers, general public, media	
DS1.5	Project dissemination material	WP1	Project	Text, images, videos	xml, png, PDF, mp4, printed material	<1TB	All	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers, general public, media	

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS1.6	Internal stakeholder overview	WP1	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	All	none	To complete stakeholder engagement tasks, personal data will be collected and stored. No contact details will be collected or stored, unless provided by the individuals with their consent and for specific activities.
DS1.7	Registration data and contact details of participants in the Diamond OA festivals and the final conference	WP1	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	All	none	Personal data will be collected and stored to ensure participants are managed and informed about the event details. No contact details will be collected or stored, unless provided by the individuals with their consent.
DS2.1	Public consultation and validation event dataset on DOAS adaptations for books	WP2	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO1	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers	Aggregated/anonymised results open (CC BY 4.0); microdata restricted (GDPR). Responsible partner: OAPEN

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS2.2	Certification database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component	WP2	Project	Text, Database	csv, txt	<1GB	SO1	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers	Journal/publisher-level data; sensitivity of individual results to be assessed. Responsible partner: DOAJ
DS2.3	Mapping of Open Science policies including DOAS criteria across ERA countries	WP2	Project	Text, List	csv, xlsx	<1GB	SO1; SO4	Researchers; Policymakers; Funders; Public; National Capacity Centres	Based entirely on publicly available policy documents; no personal data involved. Responsible partner: FECYT
DS2.4	Certification framework. Applicant data and evaluation records; Diamond OA Observatory aggregated monitoring dataset	WP2	Project	Database, aggregated data	csv, txt	<1GB	SO1	none (restricted access)	Personal data (name, email, institution) collected under GDPR. Data will be anonymised prior to any internal sharing. Access limited to designated evaluators. Responsible partner: FECYT

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS3.1	"Train-the-Trainers" sessions and Certification framework — participant data and evaluation records	WP3	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO2	none	
DS3.2	Training material	WP3	Project	Text	PDF; H5P	<1GB	SO2	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers	Structure and content of learning modules. Available on Zenodo and via the EDCH training platform
DS3.3	Survey about upskilling of OA publishing trainers (needs and motivation analysis)	WP3	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO2	none	Personal data (name, email, institution) collected under GDPR. Access limited to designated evaluators.
DS4.1	DDH User database (trusted source, editor, administrator)	WP4	EDCH	Databa se	db tables	<1GB	n/a	DDH administration team	
DS4.2	DDH Diamond journal database	WP4	EDCH	Databa se	db tables	<1GB	SO4	Researchers, Publishers/ Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers, general public, media	

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS4.3	Guide to scholarly indexes	WP4	EDCH/ OpenE dition	Databa se, Text, List	Sheet, xlsx, md	<1GB	SO3	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers, general public, media	
DS4.4	Task 4.1 dissemination list to communicate work results and to gather input and feedback - will include non-consortium members	WP4	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO3	none	
DS4.5	WP dissemination list	WP4	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO4	none	
DS4.6	OJS preconfiguration & prepackaging	WP4	Project	Softwa re, Text	php source code	<1GB	SO2; SO3	global community of OJS-using publishers	
DS5.1	EDCH Forum User Database	WP5	EDCH	Databa se, List	csv	<1GB	SO4	Forum administration team	Additional entries to the user database, generated throughout the project
DS5.2	EDCH Registry User Database	WP5	EDCH	Databa se	csv, xlsx	<1GB	SO4	Registry administration team	Additional entries to the user database

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS5.3	National Capacity Centres Network member data	WP5	Project	List	csv, xlsx	<1GB	All	None	Contact details of NCCs that are not participating in the project
DS5.4	Contact details for the Directory of INPOA publishing professionals	WP5	Project	List	csv	<1GB	SO2		Contact details of publishing specialists
DS5.5	Workshop/event s registration data	WP5	Project + partici pants	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	All	None	
DS5.6	Data on mobility frameworks and projects for higher education students and staff	WP5	Project	List	csv	<1GB	All	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers	
DS5.7	EDCH Registry Organisation Database	WP5	EDCH	List	csv	<1GB	SO4	Researchers, INPOA Publishers and Service Providers, Funders, Policymakers	Additional entries to the organisation database, generated throughout the project
DS6.1	Workshop registrations data	WP6	Project /attend ees	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO4	None	

Internal Id	Description	WP	Prove nance	Type	Format	Size	Relation to project objectives	Potential users beyond the project	Remarks
DS6.2	Possible stakeholders survey and/or interviews data (to be confirmed)	WP6	Project + partici pants	Text, Table	csv, txt	<1GB	SO4	None	
DS6.3	WP dissemination list	WP6	Project	Text, List	csv, txt	<1GB	SO4	None	

Legend: Project strategic objectives

S01: To enhance quality assessment and monitoring

S02: To upscale skills and competences

S03: To offer access to publishing tools

S04: To provide guidance, coordination and alignment across the ERA

2.3 Findable

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	N/A		No	No
DS1.2	Project deliverables	DOI	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines)	Yes	Yes
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS1.4	Project website and the information contained therein	N/A	N/A	Yes	Yes
DS1.5	Project dissemination material	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS1.6	Internal stakeholder overview	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS1.7	Registration data and contact details of participants in the Diamond OA festivals and the final conference	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS2.1	Public consultation and validation event dataset on DOAS adaptations for books	DOI (aggregated dataset on Zenodo)	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines)	Yes	Yes
DS2.2	Certification exercise database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component, from the certification exercise (T2.2)	DOI (Zenodo)	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines)	Yes	Yes

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS2.3	Mapping of Open Science policies including DOAS criteria across ERA countries (T2.3)	DOI (Zenodo)	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines)	Yes	Yes
DS2.4	Diamond OA Observatory aggregated monitoring dataset	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS3.1	"Train-the-Trainers" sessions and Certification framework — participant data and evaluation records	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS3.2	Training material	DOI (PDF)	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines)	Yes	Yes
DS3.3	Survey about upskilling of OA publishing trainers (needs and motivation analysis)	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS4.1	DDH User database (trusted source, editor, administrator)	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS4.2	DDH Diamond journal database	ISSN	Dublin Core, JMEF	Yes	Yes
DS4.3	Guide to scholarly indexes	DOI (Zenodo, xlsx only)	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines, xlsx only)	Yes	Yes
DS4.4	Task dissemination list (Task 4.1) to communicate work results and to gather input and feedback	N/A	N/A	No	No

Internal ID	Description	Pid	Metadata standards	Keywords	Machine readable metadata?
DS4.5	WP dissemination list	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS4.6	OJS preconfiguration & prepackaging	N/A	N/A	Yes	Yes
DS5.1	EDCH Forum User Database	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.2	EDCH Registry User Database	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.3	National Capacity Centres Network member data	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.4	Contact details for the Directory of INPOA publishing professionals	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.5	Workshop/events registrations data	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.6	Data on mobility frameworks and projects for higher education students and staff	DOI	DataCite, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines)	Yes	Yes
DS5.7	EDCH Registry Organisation Database	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS6.1	Workshop registrations data	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS6.2	Possible stakeholders survey and/or interviews data (to be confirmed)	DOI	Dublin Core	Yes	Yes
DS6.3	WP dissemination list	N/A	N/A	No	No

2.4 Accessible

Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	Confidential for the internal management of the project and EC audits	N/A	Login/Password	Project Manager	N/A	N/A	>=5 years after the end of the project	N/A	No
DS1.2	Project deliverables	Zenodo; project shared drive	No	Yes	Yes	N/A	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC0	Undefined	No	No
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	Confidential for the internal management of the project and EC audit	N/A	Login/Password	Project Manager	N/A	N/A	>=5 years after the end of the project	No	No
DS1.4	Project website and the information contained therein	Host server for edch.eu	N/A	N/A	Yes	N/A	HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	>=5 years after the end of the project	No	No
DS1.5	Project dissemination material	Project shared drive; host server for edch.eu (for part of the materials)	N/A	N/A	Yes	N/A	HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC0	>=5 years after the end of the project	No	No

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Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Commit fee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS1.6	Internal stakeholder overview	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	N/A	Login/Password	Project Manager	N/A	N/A	End of the project	N/A	No
DS1.7	Registration data and contact details of participants in the Diamond OA festivals and the final conference	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	N/A	Login/Password	N/A	N/A	N/A	End of the project	N/A	No
DS2.1	Public consultation and validation event dataset on DOAS adaptations for books	Zenodo (aggregated dataset); project shared Drive (microdata)	No	Yes	Yes	Partially public (aggregated results open; microdata restricted) GDPR; raw responses contain personal data (name, institution, country)	OAI-PMH; HTTPS (aggregated dataset)	Login/Password (microdata)	T2.1 leader (OAPEN)	N/A	CC0	>=5 years after the end of the project	No	No

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Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS2.2	Certification exercise database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component, from the certification exercise (T2.2)	Zenodo	No	Yes	Yes	N/A	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	N/A	DOAJ (T2.2 leader)	N/A	CC0	Undefined	No	No
DS2.3	Mapping of Open Science policies including DOAS criteria across ERA countries (T2.3)	Zenodo	No	Yes	Yes	N/A	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC0	Undefined	No	No
DS2.4	Diamond OA Observatory aggregated monitoring dataset	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR; restricted to authorised evaluators; anonymised internally	N/A	Login/Password	FECYT (T3.4 leader) / designated evaluator committee	N/A	N/A	End of the project	No	No

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Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Commit fee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS3.1	"Train-the-Trainers" sessions and Certification framework; participant data and evaluation records	Project shared drive; moodle	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR restrictions	N/A	Login/Password	Task 3.1 leader	N/A	N/A	End of the project	No	No
DS3.2	Training material	Zenodo; Moodle	No	Yes	Yes	N/A	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC0	Undefined	N/A	
DS3.3	Survey about upskilling of OA publishing trainers (needs and motivation analysis)	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR restrictions	N/A	Login/Password	Task 3.1 leader	N/A	N/A	End of the project	N/A	No
DS4.1	DDH User database (administrator)	https://ddh.edch.eu (but only accessible to administrators) (hosted on ICM UW server infrastructure)	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR restrictions	N/A	Login/Password	Task 4.1 Leader	N/A	N/A	Undefined	No	Yes

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Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS4.2	DDH Diamond journal database	https://ddh.edch.eu (hosted on ICM UW server infrastructure)	N/A	N/A	Yes		HTTPS; OAI-PMH	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Undefined	No	Yes
DS4.3	Guide to scholarly indexes	Zenodo (xlsx only), GitHub (md only)	No	Yes	Yes		HTTPS; OAI-PMH	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC BY 4.0	Undefined	No	No
DS4.4	Task dissemination list (Task 4.1) to communicate work results and to gather input and feedback	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR restrictions	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	End of the project	N/A	No
DS4.5	WP dissemination list	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR restrictions	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Undefined	N/A	No
DS4.6	OJS preconfiguration & prepackaging	Github	N/A	N/A	Yes		HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Undefined	Yes	No
DS5.1	EDCH Forum User Database	Host server for forum.edch.eu	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	HTTPS	Login/Password	Administrator	N/A	N/A	Undefined	No	No

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Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS5.2	EDCH Registry User Database	Host server for registry.edch.eu	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	HTTPS	Login/Password	Administrator	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.3	National Capacity Centres Network member data	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	N/A	Login/Password	Administrator	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.4	Contact details for the Directory of INPOA publishing professionals	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.5	Workshop/events registrations data	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No	GDPR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No
DS5.6	Data on mobility frameworks and projects for higher education students and staff	Zenodo	No	Yes	Yes		OAI-PMH; HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC0	N/A	No	No

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Internal ID	Description	Repository / Storage	Specific Arrangement with repository	Does the repository resolve the dataset Pid	Open	Legal and contractual restrictions	Open access protocol to data	Restricted access protocol	Restricted Access Contact Point	Restricted Access Committee?	Metadata License	Duration of availability (data and metadata)	Delivery of Software to read the data?	Software documentation included?
DS5.7	EDCH Registry Organisation Database	Host server for registry.edch.eu	N/A	N/A	Yes		HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Undefined	No	No
DS6.1	Workshop registrations data	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No		N/A	Login/Password	N/A	N/A	N/A	End of the project	No	No
DS6.2	Possible stakeholders survey and/or interviews data (to be confirmed)	Zenodo	N/A	Yes	Yes	Only anonymized survey data if a survey is conducted. Interview data would not be made public.	OAI-PMH; HTTPS	N/A	N/A	N/A	CC-BY	Undefined	No	No
DS6.3	WP dissemination list	Project shared drive	N/A	N/A	No		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	End of the project	No	No

2.5 Interoperable

Internal ID	Description	Standard ontologies, vocabularies and formats used	If uncommon, mapping to standard ontologies?	Qualified references to other data from the project?
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	N/A	N/A	No
DS1.2	Project deliverables	DataCite, Dublin Core (Zenodo)	N/A	Shared Community on Zenodo
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	N/A	N/A	No
DS1.4	Project website and the information contained therein	N/A	N/A	No
DS1.5	Project dissemination material	N/A	N/A	No
DS1.6	Internal stakeholder overview	N/A	N/A	No
DS1.7	Registration data and contact details of participants in the Diamond OA festivals and the final conference	N/A	N/A	No

Internal ID	Description	Standard ontologies, vocabularies and formats used	If uncommon, mapping to standard ontologies?	Qualified references to other data from the project?
DS2.1	Certification exercise database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component, from the certification exercise (T2.2)	DataCite, Dublin Core (Zenodo)	N/A	Shared Community on Zenodo; To be potentially processed by other WP tasks
DS2.2	Certification exercise database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component, from the certification exercise (T2.2)	DataCite, Dublin Core, CSV/XLSX; ISSN identifier	N/A	Shared Community on Zenodo; To be potentially processed by other WP tasks
DS2.3	Mapping of Open Science policies including DOAS criteria across ERA countries (T2.3)	DataCite, Dublin Core	N/A	Shared Community on Zenodo; To be potentially processed by other WP tasks
DS2.4	Diamond OA Observatory aggregated monitoring dataset	N/A	N/A	No
DS3.1	"Train-the-Trainers" sessions and Certification framework — participant data and evaluation records	N/A	N/A	No
DS3.2	Training material	Datacite, Dublin Core (PDF)	N/A	Shared Community on Zenodo

Internal ID	Description	Standard ontologies, vocabularies and formats used	If uncommon, mapping to standard ontologies?	Qualified references to other data from the project?
DS3.3	Survey about upskilling of OA publishing trainers (needs and motivation analysis)	N/A	N/A	No
DS4.1	DDH User database (trusted source, editor, administrator)	N/A	N/A	No
DS4.2	DDH Diamond journal database	Dublin Core, JMEF	N/A	No
DS4.3	Guide to scholarly indexes	Datacite, Dublin Core (xlsx only)	N/A	No
DS4.4	Task dissemination list (Task 4.1) to communicate work results and to gather input and feedback	N/A	N/A	No
DS4.5	WP dissemination list	N/A	N/A	No
DS4.6	OJS preconfiguration & prepackaging	N/A	N/A	No
DS5.1	EDCH Forum User Database	N/A	N/A	No
DS5.2	EDCH Registry User Database	N/A	N/A	No
DS5.3	National Capacity Centres Network member data	N/A	N/A	No

Internal ID	Description	Standard ontologies, vocabularies and formats used	If uncommon, mapping to standard ontologies?	Qualified references to other data from the project?
DS5.4	Contact details for the Directory of INPOA publishing professionals	N/A	N/A	No
DS5.5	Workshop/events registrations data	N/A	N/A	No
DS5.6	Data on mobility frameworks and projects for higher education students and staff	DataCite, Dublin Core	N/A	No
DS5.7	EDCH Registry Organisation Database	N/A	N/A	No
DS6.1	Workshop registrations data	N/A	N/A	No
DS6.2	Possible stakeholders survey and/or interviews data (to be confirmed)	Dublin Core	N/A	No
DS6.3	WP dissemination list	N/A	N/A	No

2.6 Reusable

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accessible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	Quality and Risk Management Plan	N/A	EC auditors	N/A	N/A
DS1.2	Project deliverables	N/A	CC BY	Yes	N/A	External Review. See QRMP
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	Quality and Risk Management Plan	N/A	EC auditors	N/A	Internal audit
DS1.4	Project website and the information contained therein	N/A	CC BY	Yes	N/A	Proof reading, internal reviews
DS1.5	Project dissemination material	Project Engagement and Dissemination Report	CC BY	Yes	N/A	Proof reading, internal reviews
DS1.6	Internal stakeholder overview	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review
DS1.7	Registration data and contact details of participants in the Diamond OA festivals and the final conference	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accessible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS2.1	Public consultation and validation event dataset on DOAS adaptations for books	Methodology description, data dictionary	CC BY 4.0 (aggregated open data); N/A (restricted microdata)	Yes (the aggregated version)	N/A	Internal review by T2.1 partners; anonymisation and validation prior to publication (if needed)
DS2.2	Certification exercise database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component, from the certification exercise (T2.2)	Methodology description, data dictionary	CC BY 4.0	Yes	DOAS version used	Internal review by T2.2 partners
DS2.3	Mapping of Open Science policies including DOAS criteria across ERA countries (T2.3)	Methodology description, data dictionary	CC BY	Yes	Yes	Internal review by T2.3 partners
DS2.4	Diamond OA Observatory aggregated monitoring dataset	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review by evaluators

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accessible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS3.1	"Train-the-Trainers" sessions and Certification framework — participant data and evaluation records	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review
DS3.2	Training material	N/A	CC BY	Yes	Yes	Internal review, external review
DS3.3	Survey about upskilling of OA publishing trainers (needs and motivation analysis)	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review
DS4.1	DDH User database (trusted source, editor, administrator)	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A
DS4.2	DDH Diamond journal database	API description: https://ddh.edch.eu/docs/oai-api-documentation/	(TBD)	Yes	Yes	DDH journal verification team, trusted sources
DS4.3	Guide to scholarly indexes	N/A	CC BY	Yes	Yes	Internal review

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accessible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS4.4	Task dissemination list (Task 4.1) to communicate work results and to gather input and feedback	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A
DS4.5	WP dissemination list	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A
DS4.6	OJS preconfiguration & prepackaging	N/A	GPL	Yes	N/A	Internal review, external review
DS5.1	EDCH Forum User Database	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review
DS5.2	EDCH Registry User Database	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review
DS5.3	National Capacity Centres Network member data	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A
DS5.4	Contact details for the Directory of INPOA publishing professionals	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	Internal review
DS5.5	Workshop/events registrations data	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A

Internal ID	Description	Description of documentation provided to support reuse	License on data	Data accessible to third parties post-project?	Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Data quality assurance process
DS5.6	Data on mobility frameworks and projects for higher education students and staff	N/A	CC BY	Yes	N/A	External Review. See QRMP
DS5.7	EDCH Registry Organisation Database	N/A	CC BY	Yes	N/A	Internal review
DS6.1	Workshop registrations data	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A
DS6.2	Possible stakeholders survey and/or interviews data (to be confirmed)	N/A	CC-BY	Yes	Yes	Internal review
DS6.3	WP dissemination list	N/A	N/A	No	N/A	N/A

2.7 Cost, Security, and Ethics

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS1.1	Meeting notes and minutes	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	None	Personal, confidential, or financial data
DS1.2	Project deliverables	N/A	Public deliverables are hosted on Zenodo, where they are receiving a DOI. Non-public deliverables are only circulated to the authorised contacts. The deliverable template is kept in the project Google Shared drive.	Zenodo	None	None
DS1.3	Technical reports and financial data	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	None	Personal, confidential, or financial data
DS1.4	Project website and the information contained therein	N/A	Drupal built-in features; Data security measures of host institution	None	None	None

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS1.5	Project dissemination material	N/A	[Online versions] Drupal built-in features; Data security measures of host institution	None	None	None
DS1.6	Internal stakeholder overview	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS1.7	Registration data and contact details of participants in the Diamond OA festivals and the final conference	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS2.1	Public consultation and validation event dataset on DOAS adaptations for books	N/A	Personal data stored in a secure, access-controlled environment (project Google Shared Drive, restricted access). Responses anonymised prior to any internal sharing or publication. Survey platform compliant with GDPR. Authentication required for access to microdata.	Zenodo (aggregated data)	GDPR —applies to raw consultation responses containing personal data (name, institution, country); only aggregated/anonymised data shared openly	GDPR —applies to personal data collected during the public consultation

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS2.2	Certification exercise database: DOAS compliance results per journal/publisher and DOAS component, from the certification exercise (T2.2)	N/A	Data stored in project-secured environment prior to publication (if needed); access controlled during the certification exercise	Zenodo	No personal data; sensitivity of institutional results to be assessed and managed (anonymisation if needed)	None —dataset only contains institutional data
DS2.3	Mapping of Open Science policies including DOAS criteria across ERA countries (T2.3)	N/A	Data stored in a project-secured environment prior to publication; access controlled during the certification exercise. Publicly available in Zenodo upon publication	Zenodo	Dataset based on public documents. No personal or sensitive data involved	None —all documents are publicly available
DS2.4	Diamond OA Observatory aggregated monitoring dataset	N/A	Data stored in a secure, access-controlled environment. Personal data anonymised before sharing with evaluators. Authentication required for access.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS3.1	"Train-the-Trainers" sessions and Certification framework — participant data and evaluation records	N/A	Moodle built-in features; data security measures of host institution; data are anonymized	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS3.2	Training material	N/A	Data stored in project-secured environment prior to publication (if needed)	Zenodo	None	None

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS3.3	Survey about upskilling of OA publishing trainers (needs and motivation analysis)	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS4.1	DDH User database (trusted source, editor, administrator)	N/A	Data only accessible to administrators; data security measures of host institution (ICM UW)	database backups	GDPR	GDPR
DS4.2	DDH Diamond journal database	N/A	Data security measures of host institution	database backups	None	None
DS4.3	Guide to scholarly indexes	N/A	Data security measures of Zenodo	Zenodo	None	None
DS4.4	Task dissemination list (Task 4.1) to communicate work results and to gather input and feedback	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS4.5	WP dissemination list	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS4.6	OJS preconfiguration & prepackaging	N/A	Data security measures of host platform (Github)	None	None	None
DS5.1	EDCH Forum User Database	N/A	Discourse built-in features; Data security measures of host institution (platform providers)	database backups	GDPR	GDPR
DS5.2	EDCH Registry User Database	N/A	Drupal built-in features; Data security measures of host institution (PCSS)	database backups	GDPR	GDPR
DS5.3	National Capacity Centres Network member data	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS5.4	Contact details for the Directory of INPOA publishing professionals	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS5.5	Workshop/events registrations data	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR

Internal ID	Description	Costs of FAIR (direct and indirect)	Provision of data security	Long term preservation	Ethics issues impeding sharing	Legal issues impeding sharing
DS5.6	Data on mobility frameworks and projects for higher education students and staff	N/A	Public dataset available on Zenodo, where it is assigned a DOI. The source file is kept in the project Google Drive	Zenodo	None	None
DS5.7	EDCH Registry Organisation Database	N/A	Data security measures of host institution	database backups	None	None
DS6.1	Workshop registrations data	N/A	Data security measures of host institution	None	GDPR	GDPR
DS6.2	Possible stakeholders survey and/or interviews data (to be confirmed)	N/A	Public dataset available on Zenodo, where it is assigned a DOI. The source file is kept in the project Google Drive	Zenodo	None as data will be anonymized	None
DS6.3	WP dissemination list	N/A	Stored in a dedicated Google Shared Drive managed by the Coordinator. Access is restricted to a limited set of participants and authentication with a Google account is required. Access to third parties is granted upon request.	None	GDPR	GDPR